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COMPARISON BETWEEN GENETIC FUZZY METHODOLOGY AND Q-LEARNING FOR COLLABORATIVE CONTROL DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

A comparison between two machine learning approaches viz., Genetic Fuzzy Methodology and Q-learning, is presented in this paper. The approaches are used to model controllers for a set of collaborative robots that need to work together to bring an object to a target position. The robots are fixed and are attached to the object through elastic cables. A major constraint considered in this problem is that the robots cannot communicate with each other. This means that at any instant, each robot has no motion or control information of the other robots and it can only pull or release its cable based only on the motion states of the object. This decentralized control problem provides a good example to test the capabilities and restrictions of these two machine learning approaches. The system is first trained using a set of training scenarios and then applied to an extensive test set to check the generalization achieved by each method.

KEYWORDS

Genetic fuzzy system, Q-learning, reinforcement learning, collaborative robotics, decentralized control.

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AN OBNOXIOUS LACUNA ON DISCOURSES AND COUNTER DISCOURSES OVER ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence is the highest form of human development and sound outcome of human conscience till the date. But the very development seems to be devastating to human future ahead and has been heavily projected accordingly. More than it may be to decay and destroy the world, the negative and chilling views on the prospective damages of AI that scholars are percolating to public are costing many times on humans; and that is plunging human mindset into irreparable pessimism and negativity. This article explores the way that AI is being depressingly explored and investigated to browbeat public. In addition, this write-up highlights the serious lacuna, which the advanced academic engagement has still grossly failed to fill up, of a great deal in course of mainstreaming views and discussions for noble cause of human development and societal well-belling . Further, it unmasks the dire need in making constructive, encouraging and optimistic mind-set building academic pursuits and writings then makes an alarming call to the all prominent scholars to engage with due compliance of it

Method and Hypothesis

As a doctrinal qualitative research based on extensive survey of secondary data and literature, methodologically, with adoption of paradigm of descriptive interpretation, this research hypothesizes that the discussions and discourses over AI are biased, hold a serious lacuna thus need to be reconstructed to make it balanced and build better world than to browbeat people.

KEYWORDS

Artificial Intelligence, Human Future, Economic Development, Job Market

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EXTRACTIVE SUMMARIZATION WITH VERY DEEP PRETRAINED LANGUAGE MODEL

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ABSTRACT

Recent development of generative pretrained language models has been proven very successful on a wide range of NLP tasks, such as text classification, question answering, textual entailment and so on. In this work, we present a two-phase encoder decoder architecture based on Bidirectional Encoding Representation from Transformers (BERT) for extractive summarization task. We evaluated our model by both automatic metrics and human annotators, and demonstrated that the architecture achieves the state-of-the-art comparable result on large scale corpus - CNN/Daily Mail. As the best of our knowledge, this is the first work that applies BERT based architecture to a text summarization task and achieved the state-of-the-art comparable result.

KEYWORDS

BERT, AI, Deep Learning, Summarization.

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ADAPTIVE LEARNING EXPERT SYSTEM FOR DIAGNOSIS AND MANAGEMENT OF VIRAL HEPATITIS

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ABSTRACT

Viral hepatitis is the regularly found health problem throughout the world among other easily transmitted diseases, such as tuberculosis, human immune virus, malaria and so on. Among all hepatitis viruses, the uppermost numbers of deaths are result from the long-lasting hepatitis C infection or long-lasting hepatitis B. In order to develop this system, the knowledge is acquired using both structured and semi-structured interviews from internists of St.Paul Hospital. Once the knowledge is acquired, it is modeled and represented using rule based reasoning techniques. Both forward and backward chaining is used to infer the rules and provide appropriate advices in the developed expert system. For the purpose of developing the prototype expert system SWI-prolog editor also used. The proposed system has the ability to adapt with dynamic knowledge by generalizing rules and discover new rules through learning the newly arrived knowledge from domain experts adaptively without any help from the knowledge engineer.

KEYWORDS

Expert System, Diagnosis and Management of Viral Hepatitis, Adaptive Learning, Discovery and Generalization Mechanism

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MODELLING OF INTELLIGENT AGENTS USING A-PROLOG

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, research in artificial intelligence has widely grown in areas such as knowledge representation, goal-directed behaviour and knowledge reusability, all of them directly relevant to improving intelligent agents in computer games. In a particular way, we focus on the development of a novel algorithm that allow an agent to combine fundamental theories such as reasoning, learning and simulation. This algorithm combines a system of logical rules and a simulation mechanism based on learning that makes our agent has an infallible mechanism for decision-making into the game “connect four”. The logic system is developed in a modelling language known as Answer Set Programming or A-Prolog. This paradigm is the integration of two well-known languages, namely Prolog and ASP.

KEYWORDS

Agents, Games, A-Prolog, Answer Set Programming & Logic Programming

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AN ONLINE EXPERT SYSTEM FOR PSYCHIATRIC DIAGNOSIS

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ABSTRACT

Expert systems are programs that use artificial intelligence techniques, and simulate the performance of the human expert in a given area of expertise by collecting and using one or more expert information and expertise in a particular field. We developed declarative, online procedural rule-based expert system models for psychological diseases diagnosis and classification. The constructed system exploited computer as an intelligent and deductive tool. This system diagnoses and treats more than four types of psychiatric diseases, i.e., depression, anxiety disorder, obsessive-compulsive disorder, and hysteria. The system helps psychology practitioner and doctors to diagnose the condition of a patient efficiently and in short time. It is also very useful for the patients who cannot go to a doctor because they cannot afford the cost, or they do not have a psychological clinic in their area, or they are ashamed of discussing their situation with a doctor. The system consists of program codes that make a logic decision to classify the problem of the patient. The methodology for developing the declarative model was based on the backward chaining, also called goal-driven reasoning, where knowledge is represented by a set of IF-THEN production rules. The declarative programs were written in the PROLOG. While the design of the procedural model was based on using common languages like PHP, JavaScript, CSS, and HTML. The user of the system will enter the symptoms of the patients through the user interface and the program executes. Then the program links the symptoms to the pre-programmed psychological diseases, and will classify the disease and recommend treatment.

The proposed online system link: <http://esp-online.site/>

KEYWORDS

Artificial Intelligence, Expert systems, Medical Diagnosis, Rules, Symbolic Reasoning, psychiatric diseases.

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